

INCREASING THE PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF THE STUDENTS OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION.

Teacher of Preschool Education Methodology at Termiz State
Pedagogical Institute
Mamatkulova Shakhnoza O'ktam qizi

Annotation: At a time when our rapidly developing country is undergoing great changes, the issue of radical reform of the pre-school education system has become a priority. On December 29, 2016, the publication of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-2707 "On measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021" improvement, education of preschool children, formation of skills and abilities, as well as re-examination of state requirements for preparation for school education. Accordingly, educators and specialists have carefully studied the experience of foreign education and began to apply it in their pedagogical process.

Keywords: education, upbringing, child, collaboration, process, educator, parent, early childhood, mental development.

Preschool education is the primary form of continuing education. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" also states that "preschool education aims to form a child's personality in a healthy and mature, ready for school." The content of parental referrals to psychologists has changed slightly and become more specific. Parents' interest in a practical psychologist has increased significantly. There is a growing interest in psychological services in order to increase the psychological competence of parents.

The first group of appeals is of a cognitive nature. Realizing the need to monitor a child's mental development, parents turn to a psychologist with the problem of determining their child's level of mental and intellectual development. In addition, as the number of popular science books, articles, and special television programs on the role of preschool childhood in the formation of a person's

personality and mental development increases, so does the mental competence of parents, which helps to determine the mental processes in their children is evidence of growing interest.

The second group of appeals consists of appeals to determine the abilities of children. As a result of changes in the education system, many parents are beginning to realize the need to prepare their children for school much earlier.

The increase in the number of different child development clubs for preschool children and the increase in parents' knowledge of psychology, therefore, in order to determine the level of development of their children's abilities at the age of 3-4 and to prepare their children for education from an early age. the need for a specialist increased. Psychologists of preschool education institutions should conduct special, methodical, program-based monitoring of the development of the child's ability to perform certain activities - to identify children who are developing signs of ability.

The third group of complaints includes complaints from parents due to deviations in the child's behavior. At the same time, parents mainly address children's aggression, shyness, fantasies, emotional instability, nervousness.

The third group of complaints includes complaints from parents due to deviations in the child's behavior. At the same time, parents mainly address children's aggression, shyness, fantasies, emotional instability, nervousness.

Psychologists divide the underlying causes of behavioral disorders in children into three groups.

Parents do not know the laws of mental development of the child; (As a result of ignorance of the laws of development, parents make age-inappropriate demands on children, and consider changes in times of crisis as mental disorders).

Neuropsychiatric disorders in the child (they are neuroses, psychosomatic diseases. There may be complications of mental retardation. At this time, the psychologist should advise parents to consult their specialist, ie a neurologist).

Controversial, restless family environment. Educators also consult a psychologist in a preschool organization. Many educators are concerned about children with aggressive or cognitive disabilities, as both groups of children make group learning more difficult. Along with parents, educators are also interested in the child's level of mental development, and parents need to work effectively with psychologists. The preschool psychologist should also plan individual counseling with parents on the agenda. In addition, the director of the preschool organization should create the necessary conditions for the work of a psychologist. In turn, the psychologist of the preschool organization should study the psychological aspects of the psychological process of first-year children in the organization. In this regard, the psychologist of the preschool organization should also establish cooperation with parents, neighborhoods, schools and family clinics.

Collaboration of the psychologist of the preschool organization with parents. The role of the family in the early stages of a child's development is invaluable. Children are raised in a family, and the events that take place in them have a profound effect on them. Young children are very attached to the family because the family: Provides them with physical fitness, food, clothing, shelter, and health care; It shows their emotional endurance, including kindness, support, and constantly reminds them of what is good and what is bad. It provides the conditions for their development. It is important that educators recognize the leading role of the family as the child's first naturalist. By the time the child arrives in the small group of the preschool, the family environment (healthy or unhealthy) will be ingrained in the child's mind. There is no doubt that the child's perception of the external environment, the attitude of others to him, communication with peers, the first knowledge of the learning process in a correct and interesting way, is properly organized in collaboration with pedagogical psychologists and the family. It is important to note the differences in the results achieved in different areas of children's development under the influence of

different conditions of home education. It is necessary to take into account these features of pre-school children in the educational process, not to develop them mentally at the request of parents, but to solve general developmental tasks, the full development of the child's personality. Socio-psychological protection, the success of a child's success depends on who and how influences him. The child spends most of his time in the preschool and at home, so the influence of educators and parents should not be contradictory, but should be positively and actively perceived by the child. This can only be achieved if educators and parents work together and solve educational problems together. Socio-pedagogical work with families, which involves the involvement of parents in the organization of the educational process and the direct pedagogical process itself, teaching them the forms of developmental interactions with children, methodological assistance in the education of children should pay great attention to the importance of work. In order to be effective and involve the family in the work of the MTT, educators need to know the primary responsibilities of the children they are raising, and to have a clear idea of their family and close relatives.

Collaboration of the psychologist of the preschool organization with school, community and family polyclinics.

Some information about a toddler who has taken the first step in preschool can be obtained from the child's psychologist in the neighborhood where the child lives, his or her marital status, place in the community, and the mental state of the parents, and educational work with the child. An important aspect of family clinics is that the doctor of the polyclinic collects information about the development of the child in the womb, the condition after birth, the normal stages of development. If there are problems with the child's psyche or the parents' mental state, the cooperation of the outpatient doctor and the preschool psychologist is very important for the child's health.

According to experts, the first period of infancy ends when a child reaches the age of majority. The period from 1 to 3 years old is usually called the first age. The period from 1 to 3 years of age is of special importance in human ontogenesis, because during this period one can observe changes in the most important personality traits, such as character, attitude to the environment and others. In addition, two achievements of preschool children aged 1-3 years are observed in the acquisition of the native language and the rapid development of speech at this age. By the age of two, children will know the names of actions. At this age, a child's vocabulary has a vocabulary of fifteen words, but the child has a high level of understanding of the world around him. By the time a child is three years old, the number of words in a child's dictionary will increase to 1,500-2,000. Along with the development of a child's speech, a healthy physical and mental development also depends on a healthy family environment. Growing up in an unhealthy environment can lead to environmental aggression. For example, it is possible to observe cases of screaming, restraint, and sometimes beatings, so that some mothers do not disturb the first-year child. But such methods do not work. First of all, the child should not be insulted or beaten. Otherwise, the child's fear, according to many psychologists, will lead to the formation of a cruel attitude to the world around him, the idea that everything can be achieved by force. comes, as well as the mother's considerable prestige in the eyes of the child. But it is also important not to give in to the whims of the child, because he must always learn to achieve what he wants in this way. Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to determine the cause of the whims, and if the child is wrong, it is enough to calm down and calmly reprimand him, without arousing fear. Taking action without knowing the cause of a child's whimsy at an early age will not work. If a child does not want to listen at all, gets upset and starts kicking with his hands and feet, the only good way to calm him down without reprimanding him is to remain silent. Of course this is a very severe punishment for a child. The child realizes that his

actions are wrong for the sake of his mother's attention. Psychologists say that parents should try to communicate with the child more than to find solutions to problems, to address him with sweet words, "you are good", to emphasize that he loves him. This will optimize the child's psyche and increase his self-confidence. Parents should set an example for their first-year children in society and in the family. Because our children are our reflection in the mirror.

References.

1. "State requirements" for primary and preschool children of the Republic of Uzbekistan. July 3, 2018.
2. The state curriculum "First step" of the Ministry of Preschool Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2018
4. Nazarova F. "Psychological services and normative documents in preschool education." 2017 y
5. M.Norbosheva "Childhood and early childhood psychology" methodical manual. 2013 y
6. Nazirova GM Textbook "Organization of the educational process in preschool education" 2014
7. F.Kadirova, Sh.Tashpolatova, M.Azamova "Preschool pedagogy" F. –T .; Manaviyat 2013
- 8.qizi Mamatkulova, S. O. (2023). IMPROVING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS BASED ON CREATIVE APPROACH. *International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4, 2(3), 42-45.*
- 9.Shakhnoza, M. (2022). IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF FIRST-YEAR CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 2(05), 121-124.*